

E-LaaS

Energy optimal urban Logistics As A Service

CONFERENCE PANEL

**12th International Scientific and Technical Conference Logistic Systems -
Theory and Practice, September 3 - 5, 2023 Warsaw (Poland)**

Energy-efficient city logistics
Polish - Swedish – Chinese discussion panel
5.09.2023 – 9.00 - 10.30 CET

SUB-REPORT FOR WP6

Authors: Emilian Szczepański, Konrad Lewczuk, Marianna Jacyna (Warsaw University of Technology)

Consultations: Balazs Kulcsar, Ivan Sanchez-Diaz, Fangting Zhou (Chalmers University of Technology), Kai Wang (Tsinghua University), Dan Zhuge (Shanghai University)

Date: 20.09.2023

Project implemented as part of the call ERA-NET Cofund Urban Accessibility and Connectivity (ENUAC China Call) organized by JPI Urban Europe and the National Natural Science Foundation of China (NSFC).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 875022.

European
Commission

Project funding information

E-Laas project is carried out in an international consortium. Project coordinator in Europe: Chalmers University of Technology (Sweden), project coordinator in China: Shanghai University (China), consortium members: Tsinghua University (China), Warsaw University of Technology (Poland), cooperation partners: Stockholms stad, Trafikkontoret (Sweden), ParkUnload (Spain), Metropolis GZM (Poland), Shanghai Urban-Rural Construction and Transportation Department (China), Volvo Group Trucks Technology and Operations (Sweden).

- *The Chinese part of the project is funded by National Natural Science Foundation of China*

- *The Swedish part of the project is funded by Swedish Energy Agency*

- *The Polish part of the project is funded by the National Science Centre, Poland (project no. 2022/04/Y/ST8/00134). The value of the co-financing is PLN 878,107.00. Project duration 27/04/2023 - 26/04/2026 (36 months).*

I. Aims of the panel

The panel discussion held as part of the 12th International Scientific and Technical Conference Logistic Systems - Theory and Practice on "Energy-efficient City Logistics" was an event in the context of urban logistics research, especially in cargo transportation. This panel was dedicated to the research project E-LaaS: Energy optimal urban logistics As A Service: In this context, the panel's objectives included:

- 1) **Discussion of problems in city logistics:** Identify and discuss the main urban logistics issues in cargo transportation. Through these discussions, it was possible to gain a more thorough understanding of the challenges facing urban logistics today, such as air pollution, traffic congestion, dynamic changes in the needs of logistics system users, or the limited availability of infrastructure and its expansion in terms of last-mile delivery.
- 2) **Presentation of the E-LaaS Project:** The panel was an excellent opportunity to present the E-LaaS: Energy optimal urban logistics As A Service research project. This aimed to raise awareness among conference attendees and online guests about an existing innovative initiative that aims to develop urban logistics and contribute to energy efficiency.
- 3) **Transfer of knowledge and experience:** The panel was an opportunity to gather opinions from experts in various fields, including researchers, practitioners, and other conference participants. The views collected can serve as a valuable source of information for further research and work on urban logistics solutions carried out under the E-Laas project.

II. Panel agenda

1. Introduction (City logistics – Emilian Szczepański, Warsaw University of Technology)
2. Cargo transport in the cities, cases for:
 - 2.1. Poland - Renata Żochowska (Silesian University of Technology),
 - 2.2. Sweden - Fangting Zhou (Chalmers University of Technology),
 - 2.3. China - Dan Zhuge (Shanghai University)
3. E-LaaS as a booster for the city logistics (presentation of E-LaaS project – Emilian Szczepański (Warsaw University of Technology)
4. Discussion (moderated by Konrad Lewczuk, Warsaw University of Technology):
 - 4.1. What are the needs and expectations of citizens, cargo recipients, suppliers, logistics operators in modern city? Are they the same? Will they change and why?
 - 4.2. Electromobility for city logistics - electricity, hydrogen, synthetic fuels. Are these a solution for cities? What risks may be associated with the energy transformation?
 - 4.3. Synergy of passenger and freight transport for better city logistics.
 - 4.4. Can artificial intelligence help city management and organize freight traffic?
 - 4.5. Is modern urban logistics intended exclusively for big cities? What solutions can be applied for "broad and flat" cities, and what for "high" cities? Which ones are for the highly developed and which for the underdeveloped areas?
5. Conclusion

III. Summary of the panel

The "Energy-efficient City Logistics" panel was an important event due to raising awareness, creating dialogue in the scientific and business community, and gathering opinions and experiences. During the panel, the main problems and challenges of city logistics were discussed, which contributed to raising awareness of the energy efficiency of logistics systems. A better understanding of city logistics issues was possible thanks to the exchange of knowledge and experience among the panellists. Presentations on specific cities in Poland (Górnośląsko-Zagłębiowska Metropolis), Sweden (Goteborg, Stockholm), and China (Shanghai) allowed the expression of a broad spectrum of tasks, different points of view, user needs and current challenges. It also made it possible to systematize problems and better identify priority areas for further research and development of the project.

The panel discussion was the venue for intense debates on critical aspects of urban logistics. Topics discussed included the needs of different stakeholder groups, electromobility, synergies between passenger and delivery transportation, the role of artificial intelligence, and the adaptation of logistics solutions to varying types of cities and areas. These debates are important contributions to developing more efficient, energy-sustainable urban logistics in the ongoing E-LaaS project.

IV. Attachments

- 1) Keynote presentation
- 2) Conference programme (in Polish)

Attachment 1:

Keynote presentation

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International Scientific Conference - 2023
Logistics Systems: Theory and Practice

**Energy-efficient city
logistics**

**Polish - Swedish - Chinese
discussion panel**

5.09.2023 – 9.00 - 10.30 CET

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*Energy optimal urban Logistics
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Energy-efficient city logistics
Polish - Swedish - Chinese discussion panel

Agenda

- 1. Introduction**
- 2. Cargo transport in the cities**
- 3. E-LaaS as a booster for the city logistics**
- 4. Discussion**
- 5. Conclusion**

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1. Introduction

Energy-efficient city logistics

**Polish - Swedish - Chinese
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The goal of city logistics is to raise the quality and attractiveness of the city, thereby ensuring transportation and service accessibility for residents and enabling manufacturing and service entities to operate while minimizing the harmful effects (pollution, congestion, safety).

**Mobility of
citizens**

**Traffic
organisation**

**Road and logistics
infrastructure**

**Telecommunications,
ICT**

**Supply of residents
with utilities**

Waste collection

Policy

**Supply chain, freight
transport**

“The process for totally optimising **the logistics and transport activities** by private companies with support of advanced information systems in urban areas considering the traffic environment, the traffic congestion, the traffic safety and the energy savings within the framework of a market economy.”

Def. by Taniguchi, E., Thompson, R. G., Yamada, T. and van Duin, R. (2001). *City logistics: Network modelling and intelligent transport systems*. Pergamon, Oxford.

Last mile deliveries

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Stakeholders

Private

Residents, cargo receivers, suppliers, service providers, logistics operators, vendors

Key objectives

Access to infrastructure, low costs, benefits, flexibility

Conflicts of interest

- *environmentally friendly transport (not cheap),*
- *traffic restriction (many customers and high transport needs)*
- *Infrastructure for pedestrians, bicycles, public transport (restrictions for transport operators)*
- ...

Public

Government
Local authorities
Administrators

Key objectives

Environmental protection, infrastructure protection, city and regional development

Public-private partnership

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Why it is important issue?

Year	Cities (%)	Towns and semi-dense areas (%)	Rural areas (%)
1975	37,3	32,2	30,5
1990	41,6	31,8	26,6
2000	44,4	30,6	25,0
2015	48,2	28,3	23,5
2030	50,9	26,9	22,2
2040	52,8	25,9	21,4
2050	54,5	24,9	20,6

■ Cities ■ Towns and semi-dense areas ■ Rural areas

Cities are key to economic development

- In 2050, it is projected that **around 80% of the population** will live in urbanised areas (Cities, Towns).
- 40 large-city members of the C40 Climate Leadership Group represent **4% of the world population but generate 18% of global GDP and 10% of global carbon emissions**
(C40 Climate Leadership Group and ARUP (2011), *Climate Action in Megacities: C40 Cities Baseline and Opportunities Version 1.0*, C40 Climate Leadership Group, www.arup.com/Publications/Climate_Action_in_Megacities.aspx).
- Cities account for an estimated **67% of global energy use and 71% of global energy-related carbon dioxide (CO2) emissions**
(International Energy Agency) (2010), *World Energy Outlook 2010*, OECD, Publishing, doi: 10.1787/weo-2010-en.
- Cargo transport in cities accounts for **around 20 - 30 % of vehicle kilometres, and last mile costs (in parcel transport) account for 50 % of distribution costs.**
(Dr. Jean-Paul Rodrigue and Dr. Laetitia Dablanc: <https://globalcitylogistics.org/home/a-freight-and-the-city/what-is-city-logistics/>).

Transport in cities is essential but has negative effects: pollution, destruction of infrastructure, congestion, traffic safety, community unrest

World population shares by degree of urbanisation, 1975-2050

Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD)

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LSSTP
2023

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Sustainable transport in cities requires an appropriate approach and conditions for implementation

Energy transition

Digital transition

Solutions for City Logistics and Last Mile Deliveries

Legislation, policy, administration

Social awareness, user involvement

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Energy transition

Energy transition is a change in energy production and use with sustainability as a primary direction.

- Reduction of energy costs
- Optimisation of consumption (including demand balance)
- Reduction of pollutant emissions
- Increased use of renewable energy
- Consumer awareness and change of habits
- Energy storage
- Reliability of supply

Cities currently account for around 75% of energy consumption, and require reliability of supply

Butera, F., Eugenio, M., Chiara, P. M., & Fabrizio, L. (2018). Energy and resource efficient urban neighbourhood design principles for tropical countries: a practitioner's guidebook. *UN Habitat*.

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City Logistics

Energy transition

- Well-developed cities (use of space, 15 minutes city)
- Infrastructure for pedestrian and cycling traffic (and others including scooters)
- Resource sharing (e.g. carpooling)

Image: Microsoft Image Library

Risks of the energy transition

- Green energy production and demand is uneven and dispersed
- Overloading of the power grid (growth of electric vehicles)
- Energy shortages - blackout

Image: Microsoft Image Library

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Improving the quality of life ..., the need for safety, mobility and development, ..., increased awareness ..., the development and availability of technology ..., innovation ..., are the factors shaping the future..

Digital transition

transitions from analog to digital

- Artificial Intelligence
- Machine Learning
- Big Data
- Blockchain
- Cloud Computing
- Digital Twins
- Virtual and augmented reality
- ...

Energy transition

SMART CITY

Due to the sustainable development and the smart world concept, urban areas are a critical area, which is why the concept of "smart city" has emerged, which concerns a specific area ...

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== SMART CITY ==

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The smart city is based on a comprehensive digital city, created by visible and measurable smart management. Various facilities are equipped with sensors to create a digital network and achieve the integration of the Internet of Things through super computing and cloud computing. The Smart City is a product of the Digital City and the Internet of Things.

This concept includes:

- People communities
- Economy
- Governance
- Natural Environment
- Built infrastructure

and **activities in:**

- Organization
- Policy
- Technology

A special place in the smart city concept has transport ... **transport** is one of the basic human needs, and **mobility** determines development and **quality of life** ...

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City Logistics

Social awareness, user involvement

- *Urbanisation*
- *Changing habits*
- *Economy on demand*
- *Transport accessibility*
- *Customer requirements*
- *E-Commerce*
- ...

Every resident is also responsible for the functioning of the city ... Residents cannot just make demands ... must adapt to the changes taking place and demonstrate social responsibility.

Citizen ... where is his place in the transport system?

- Transport operations are aimed at providing services to the public
- Infrastructure operation and system organisation are to ensure safety and availability of services
- Transport is to be friendly to residents, employees, customers

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Social awareness, user involvement

Crucial in developing environmentally friendly transport systems, but also sustainable development in general, is education and knowledge transfer ...

- Shaping social responsibility and awareness from an early age
- Promoting environmentally friendly solutions
- Supporting and motivating researchers, transfer of knowledge to society
- Creating modern study programmes at universities

Today, **environmental education** is not the same as it was a few years ago ..., it's the thought of "how to get to school, work ..." or how to reduce energy and fresh water consumption

Image: Microsoft Image Library

Image: Microsoft Image Library

Image: Microsoft Image Library

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Legislation, policy, administration

Regulation and the dynamics of transport systems development...

Rapid technological development
Changing habits of the population

↓

Requires changes to existing regulations
and the development of new ones

↓

Unfortunately, they have not kept up with
the progress

↓

The long legislative processes, public consultations, and lack of
consensus manifest themselves in backwardness and
inadequacy to current conditions.

However, there are initiatives that try to take into account the dynamics of development ...
E.g. European Green Deal

- "...more efficient use of resources through the transition to a clean, closed loop economy,
- preventing the loss of biodiversity and reducing pollution levels."

Are current activities and the legal status, infrastructure and organisation of the transport system adapted to the actual needs of the population and the market?

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Legislation, policy, administration

- Development of the energy network
- Development of infrastructure for alternative vehicles
- Intelligent Transport Systems solutions in cities
- Clean transport zones
- Consolidation centres
- Crowdsourcing
- ...

WHY?

- Implementing solutions that support urban development, improve city operations and strive to be smart requires precise and transparent laws.
- Even the best innovative solutions without the proper legal conditions can be ineffective or not implemented at all and thus wasted.
- In doing so, authorities must ensure security for service delivery.

Decisions to promote, stimulate and implement innovative and environmentally friendly transport solutions have a huge impact on the sustainability of cities and regions.

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Solutions for City Logistics and Last Mile Deliveries

- Alternatively powered vehicles
- Microhubs, Parcel lockers
- Autonomous vehicles (drones)
- Shared services, pooling, crowdsourcing
- Cargo bikes (electric)
- Intelligent infrastructure management (IoT, IoV, lol)

image: Freepik.com

Image: Microsoft Image Library

Image: Inpost/ materialy prasowe

The development of green solutions is not only about alternative fuels, it is also about transport management or modern forms of organisation.

However, they will not be properly exploited without public support and appropriate policies.

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... City Logistics, Smart City ... Sustainable Concepts ...

- it is not only about electric vehicles and fossil fuel consumption, **it is also about organisation, management and security ...**
- it is not just about the city, it is also about integration into **global supply chains ...**
- it is not only modern and fast modes of transport, but also **greater transport accessibility ...**
- it is not just technology and innovation, but also **regulation and education ...**
- it is not only machines and equipment, but also **people, their habits and needs, as well as their awareness and attitudes ...**

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2. Cargo transport in the cities

Energy-efficient city logistics

Polish - Swedish - Chinese
discussion panel

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2. Cargo transport in the cities

POLAND

Renata Żochowska

Silesian University Of Technology

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2. Cargo transport in the cities

SWEDEN

Fangting Zhou

Chalmers University Of Technology

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2. Cargo transport in the cities

CHINA

Dan Zhuge

Shanghai University

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3. E-LaaS as a booster for the city logistics

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Project participants (consortium):

Cooperation partners:

Swedish Energy Agency

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- A1) We aim to represent urban logistics missions as logistics flows.
- A2) We aim to define operational (and complementary) energy use in logistics flows.
- A3) We aim to analyze spatio-temporal energy usage in urban logistics missions and perform sensitivity analysis (grid interruption, scalability).
- A4) Energy awareness on multiple levels (from customers to authorities) is aimed to incentivize.

Create an innovative platform to minimize energy consumption in the distribution process from consolidation centers to customers' doors, facilitating energy savings at each level of distribution

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O1) Contribute to sustainable development of cities and communities

O2) Create resilient logistics methods, digital and physical infrastructure for sustainable transport solutions

O3) Develop sustainable and climate-responsive urban logistic systems

T1

Develop **energy-optimal urban logistics solutions** (from consolidation centers to doors).

T2

Develop **smart multimodal and energy optimizing micro delivery systems**.

T3

Analyze **logistics mission interruptions** and advise with reconfiguration solutions to regain energy optimality.

T4

Couple **delivery platforms and unloading zones** via charging facility to the **power grid**.

T5

Quantify demand for freight and analyze the **customer behavior change** required to run the project E-Laas.

T6

Scalability of multimodal and energy optimal distribution system.

T7

Devise new ways to enhance **societal responsibility** by E-Laas.

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WP0 Definition of scenarios and reference cases Month 1-12

WP1 Dynamic use of public urban space to foster low emissions modes for the last mile Month 4-20

WP3 Efficient and scalable models for energy minimal urban logistics services Month 8-28

WP4 Algorithms for large-scale optimization under uncertainties Month 13-31

WP5 Societal awareness and policy aspects Month 5-22

WP2 Emulated analysis of energy optimal urban logistics flows Month 11-33

WP6 Dissemination Month 1-36

2023.05 2026.04

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Methods, expected results, and impact

- Provide **new concepts for freight transport** and propose **new urban logistics solutions** to lower the environmental footprint.
- Design **an energy-based multimodal urban logistics system** and optimize it.
- Engage a wide group of **citizens and stakeholders** in **energy-aware behavior**.
- Provide new and **more detailed data** on the **energy consumption of urban logistics processes** to balance energy in the city.
- Provide **tools** to **accelerate authorities' decision-making** for sustainable use and energy and infrastructure resources management.
- Develop **new infrastructure and technologies** for **charging and delivering**, e.g., micro hubs and fulfillment centers, and modernize the power grid and link its use with logistic services to increase its reliability.
- Reduce the cost of logistics services, increase the efficiency of logistics services and the accessibility of electric vehicles.

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Thank you for your attention!

Contact information

Balazs Kulcsar (Chalmers University of Technology, coordinator): kulcsar@chalmers.se

Lu Zhen (Shanghai University): lzhen@shu.edu.cn

Kai Wang (Tsinghua University): cwangkai@tsinghua.edu.cn

Emilian Szczepański (Warsaw University of Technology): emilian.szczepanski@pw.edu.pl

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4. Discussion

Energy-efficient city logistics

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4. Discussion

What are the needs and expectations of citizens, cargo recipients, suppliers, logistics operators in modern city?
Are they the same?
Will they change and why?

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4. Discussion

Electromobility for city logistics - electricity, hydrogen, synthetic fuels.
Are these a solution for cities?
What risks may be associated with the energy transformation?

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4. Discussion

Synergy of passenger and freight transport for better
city logistics.

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4. Discussion

Can artificial intelligence help city management and
organize freight traffic?

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4. Discussion

Is modern urban logistics intended exclusively for big cities?
What solutions can be applied for "broad and flat" cities,
and what for "high" cities?
Which ones are for the highly developed and which for the
underdeveloped areas?

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5. Conclusions

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Energy - efficient city logistics

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Thank you for your attention and participation in the panel

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Attachment 2:
Conference programme (in Polish)

Międzynarodowa Konferencja Naukowo-Techniczna

XII SYSTEMY LOGISTYCZNE TEORIA I PRAKTYKA

„Resilient transport infrastructure – doświadczenia nauki i biznesu”

Program konferencji

3 – 5 września 2023, Warszawa – Józefów

Organizator:

**Wydział
Transportu**

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Polskie Towarzystwo
Logistyczne

PROGRAM RAMOWY

Niedziela, 3 września 2023 r.

16.00 – 20.00 Rejestracja uczestników / Registration

Poniedziałek, 4 września 2023 r.

9.00 – 9.30	Otwarcie konferencji / Conference opening	Sala: Constellation 1/2	
9.30 – 11.20	Sesja plenarna I / Plenary session I	Sala: Constellation 1/2	s. 4
11.20 – 11.40	Przerwa kawowa / Coffe break		
11.40 – 13.30	Sesja plenarna II / Plenary session II	Sala: Constellation 1/2	s. 4
14.00 – 15.00	Lunch		
15.15 – 16.45	Sesja I.1 <i>Nowe wyzwania dla łańcuchów dostaw</i>	Sala: Constellation 1	s. 5
	Sesja I.2 <i>Problemy decyzyjne w transporcie intermodalnym</i>	Sala: Constellation 2	s. 5
	Sesja I.3 <i>Transport kolejowy a wyzwania XXI wieku cz. 1</i>	Sala: Constellation 3	s. 6
	Sesja I.4 <i>Electronic information for combined transport (panel ELECTRA)</i>	Sala: Galaxy 3	s. 6
	Sesja I.5 <i>Panel Młodych Naukowców</i>	Sala: Galaxy 4	s. 7
16.45 – 17.00	Przerwa kawowa / Coffe break		
17.00 – 18.15	Sesja II.1 <i>Transport kolejowy a wyzwania XXI wieku cz. 2</i>	Sala: Constellation 1	s. 8
	Sesja II.2 <i>Problemy decyzyjne w transporcie publicznym cz. 1</i>	Sala: Constellation 2	s. 8
	Sesja II.3 <i>Techniczne środki transportu</i>	Sala: Constellation 3	s. 9
	Sesja II.4 <i>Systemy transportowe a potrzeby osób o ograniczonej mobilności</i>	Sala: Galaxy 3	s. 9
18.30 – 19.15	Sesja plakatowa / Poster session	Sala: Galaxy 1	s. 10
20.00	Uroczysta kolacja / Gala dinner		

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9.00 – 10.30	Sesja III.1 <i>Problemy decyzyjne w transporcie publicznym cz. 2</i>	Sala: Constellation 1	s. 12
	Sesja III.2 <i>Zrównoważony rozwój infrastruktury transportowej</i>	Sala: Constellation 2	s. 12
	Sesja III.3 <i>Transport drogowy a wyzwania XXI wieku</i>	Sala: Constellation 3	s. 13
	Sesja III.4 <i>Systemy logistyczne a wyzwania XXI wieku</i>	Sala: Galaxy 3	s. 14
	Sesja III.5 <i>Energy-efficient city logistics – E-laas (międzynarodowy panel dyskusyjny)</i>	Sala: Galaxy 4	s. 14
10.30 – 10.45	Przerwa kawowa / Coffe break		
10.45 – 12.00	Sesja plenarna III / Plenary session III	Sala: Constellation 1	s. 15
12.00 – 12.30	Zamknięcie konferencji / Conference closing	Sala: Constellation 1	

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Sesja plenarna I		Paweł Drożdziel
Sesja plenarna II		Jerzy Merkisz
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Sesja I.2	<i>Problemy decyzyjne w transporcie intermodalnym</i>	Dariusz Pyza, Renata Żochowska
Sesja I.3	<i>Transport kolejowy a wyzwania XXI wieku cz. 1</i>	Marcin Chrzan, Jakub Młyńczak
Sesja I.4	<i>Electronic information for combined transport (panel ELECTRA)</i>	Roland Jachimowski, Mariusz Kostrzewski
Sesja I.5	<i>Panel Młodych Naukowców</i>	Jolanta Żak, Mirosław Siergiejczyk
Sesja II.1	<i>Transport kolejowy a wyzwania XXI wieku cz. 2</i>	Paweł Fuć, Ewelina Sendek-Matysiak
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Sesja II.3	<i>Techniczne środki transportu</i>	Ewa Kardas-Cinal, Marcin Ślęzak
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Sesja III.3	<i>Transport drogowy a wyzwania XXI wieku</i>	Ireneusz Pielecha, Krzysztof Zboiński
Sesja III.4	<i>Systemy logistyczne a wyzwania XXI wieku</i>	Andrzej Niewczas, Anna Borucka
Sesja III.5	<i>Energy-efficient city logistics – E-laas (międzynarodowy panel dyskusyjny)</i>	Emilian Szczepański
Sesja plenarna III		Konrad Lewczuk

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9.30 – 11.20 Sesja plenarna I

Przewodniczący: Paweł Drożdziel

Sala: Constellation 1/2

Ignacy Góra

Bezpieczeństwo w systemach kolejowych
Safety in railway systems

Tomasz Jałowiec, Dariusz Grala, Katarzyna Pietrzyk-Wiszowaty

Odporność łańcuchów dostaw jako wyzwanie dla wojskowego systemu logistycznego
Supply chain resilience as a challenge for military logistics

Dariusz Mazurkiewicz

Rola pomiarów w transporcie drogowym
The role of measurements in road transport

Mirosław Siergiejczyk, Stanisław Gago

Cyberbezpieczeństwo systemów teleinformatycznych w transporcie kolejowym
Cyber security of ICT systems in rail transport

Marcin Chrzan, Tomasz Ciszewski, Waldemar Nowakowski

Wybrane aspekty badań nad bezpieczeństwem transport kolejowego
The chosen aspects of research on railroad transport safety

11.40 – 13.30 Sesja plenarna II

Przewodniczący: Jerzy Merkisz

Sala: Constellation 1/2

Andrzej Kochan

Infrastruktura cyberbezpieczeństwa w cyfrowych systemach sterowania ruchem kolejowym
Cybersecurity infrastructure in digital rail traffic control systems

Tadeusz Zieliński

Logistyczne i infrastrukturalne wyzwania sojuszniczej mobilności wojskowej
Logistic and infrastructural challenges of allied military mobility

Rafał Burdzik, Chatlin Gptarson, Hulacanva A.I. Kihana

Czy wibroakustyka będzie wspomagała badania nad zdobywaniem kosmosu? Zagadnienia transportowe i badania łazika marsjańskiego.
Will vibroacoustics support research aimed at conquering space? Research on mars rover as transportation issue.

Mirosław Antonowicz

Odporność łańcuchów dostaw z udziałem transportu kolejowego
Resilience of supply chains involving rail transport

Mariusz Kołkowski

Rozwiązania ITS jako element odpornej infrastruktury
ITS solutions as an element of resilient infrastructure

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15.15 – 16.45 Sesja I.1: Nowe wyzwania dla łańcuchów dostaw

Przewodniczący: Andrzej Świdorski, Dorota Burchart Sala: Constellation 1

Michał Olgierd Staniuk, Wiesław Staniuk

Związki przyczynowo – skutkowe i bariery w zarządzaniu multikanałowym systemem logistycznym
Cause-effect relations and barriers in the management of a multi-channel logistics system

Konrad Lewczuk

Symulacyjne wspomaganie projektowania i audytu systemów logistycznych w perspektywie Przemysłu 4.0
Simulation support for design and audit of logistics systems in the perspective of Industry 4.0

Jakub Murawski, Piotr Pryciński

Wspomaganie planowania dystrybucji ładunków w warunkach niepewnego zapotrzebowania na przewóz
Supporting cargo distribution planning, taking into account uncertain transport demand

Rafał Burdzik

Uniwersalna metoda szacowania prawdopodobieństwa transmisji patogenów podczas realizacji procesów transportowych
Universal method for estimated probability of pathogen transmission in transport processes

Piotr Folega, Dorota Burchart, Marcin Staniek

Metoda oceny ekoefektywności systemów logistyczno-transportowych
A method of eco-efficiency assessment of logistics and transport systems

15.15 – 16.45 Sesja I.2: Problemy decyzyjne w transporcie intermodalnym

Przewodniczący: Dariusz Pyza, Renata Żochowska Sala: Constellation 2

Mariusz Brzeziński, Dariusz Pyza, Mariusz Piątek

Program funkcjonalno-przestrzenny dla współczesnych terminali intermodalnych
The functional and spatial program of modern intermodal terminals

Karol Nehring, Roland Jachimowski, Michał Kłodawski

Metody optymalizacji procesu obsługi pociągu intermodalnego w terminalu
Optimization methods of intermodal train handling process in terminal

Robert Kruk, Szymon Klemba

Kryteria oceny nowych podsystemów transportu intermodalnego
Evaluation criteria for new intermodal transport subsystems

Lucyna Szacillo

Wybrane aspekty analizy ryzyka podczas realizacji procesów transportowo-przeładunkowych na terminalach intermodalnych
Selected aspects of risk analysis during the realization of transport-transshipment processes at intermodal terminals

Iouri Semenov, Ludmila Filina-Dawidowicz, Wojciech Durczak

Badania zniekształcenia informacji przy planowaniu lądowo-morskich łańcuchów transportowych
Investigations of information distortion in land-sea transport chains planning

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15.15 – 16.45 Sesja I.3: *Transport kolejowy a wyzwania XXI wieku cz. 1*

Przewodniczący: Marcin Chrzan, Jakub Młyńczak

Sala: Constellation 3

Piotr Gołębiowski

Ryzyko w planowaniu ruchu kolejowego – ocena ryzyka w planowaniu pracy drużyn pociągowych
Risk in railway traffic planning – risk assessment in planning the work of train crews

Martin Krzykowski, Rafał Burdzik, Piotr Gołębiowski

Zastosowanie teorii grafów w badaniach wpływu parametrów trasy i przepustowości linii kolejowych na średnią prędkość pojazdów szynowych w transporcie kolejowym
Application of graph theory to the study of the influence of route parameters and railway line capacity on the average speed of rail vehicles in rail transport

Łukasz Bałdyga, Adam Rosiński, Sylwester Gładys

Porównanie metod wykrywania i cyfrowego odwzorowania pojazdu kolejowego
Comparison of a railroad vehicle detection and digital mapping methods

Daud Khan, Judyta Matuszek, Katarzyna Markowska, Beniamin Stecula

Wpływ pandemii Covid-19 na funkcjonowanie kolejowych przewozów pasażerskich w Polsce
Impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on the operation of passenger rail transport in Poland

Michał Steuer, Rafał Burdzik, Andrzej Kochan

Koncepcja badań i możliwości zastosowania nawigacji satelitarnej w pozycjonowaniu i lokalizacji pojazdów szynowych w sieci kolejowej
Concept of research and possibilities of implementation of satellite navigation in positioning and localization of rail vehicles in the railroad infrastructure

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Przewodniczący: Roland Jachimowski, Mariusz Kostrzewski

Sala: Galaxy 3

Roland Jachimowski, Emilian Szczepański, Tomasz Jałowicz

Cyfryzacja procesów przewozowych w transporcie intermodalnym
Digitization of transport processes in intermodal transport

Jolanta Żak, Monika Kisiel

Zastosowanie technologii RFID do procesu przepływu bagaży na lotnisku
Applying RFID technology to the baggage flow process at the airport

Piotr Gołębiowski, Jakub Murawski, Piotr Pryciński

Cyfryzacja procesów przewozowych w transporcie kolejowym
Digitalisation of transport processes in rail transport

Piotr Pryciński, Mariusz Kostrzewski

Przegląd aktualnych rozwiązań i uwarunkowań formalno-prawnych z zakresu powszechnego wdrażania elektronicznego obiegu dokumentów w przedsiębiorstwach transportowych
The review of current solutions, formal and legal conditions in the field of widespread implementation of electronic document circulation in transport companies

Karol Nehring, Marianna Jacyna, Konrad Lewczuk, Kłodawski Michał

Obszary oraz zakres wykorzystania systemów EDI w terminalach intermodalnych
Areas and scope of using EDI systems in intermodal terminals

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15.15 – 16.45 Sesja I.5: *Panel Młodych Naukowców*

Przewodniczący: **Jolanta Żak, Mirosław Siergiejski**

Sala: Galaxy 4

Bartosz Ziemianin, Marek Karkula

Ocena zastosowania technologii RPA w automatyzacji procesów transportowych na przykładzie akwizycji danych w procesie przewozowym

Evaluation of the application of RPA technology in the automation of transport processes on the example of data acquisition in the transport process

Remigiusz Wiedemann

Metodyka priorytetowego sterowania ruchem miejskim z uwzględnieniem napelnienia środków transportu

Method of occupancy-based traffic light priority for public transport

Wojciech Miechowicz, Marcin Kiciński

Analiza popytu w regionalnych przewozach autobusowych

Passenger flows analysis in regional bus transport

Ewa Habierska, Konrad Lewczuk, Adam Rosiński

Porównanie algorytmu genetycznego i przeszukiwania tabu w planowaniu zadań pojazdów

Comparison of genetic algorithm and tabu search in vehicle task scheduling

Rafał Burdzik, Wongelawit Chema

Analiza ryzyka infekcji COVID-19, jak zmieniała się od początku do dziś

COVID-19 risk infection analysis, how it changes starting from beginning until today

Małgorzata Zysińska, Jolanta Żak

Zastosowanie autorskiej metody wieloaspektowej oceny realizacji usług w branży transportu i logistyki

Application of the author's method of multi-faceted evaluation of the services in the transport and logistics sector

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17.00 – 18.15 Sesja II.1: Transport kolejowy a wyzwania XXI wieku cz. 2

Przewodniczący: Paweł Fuć, Ewelina Sendek-Matysiak *Sala: Constellation 1*

Jacek Kukulski, Krzysztof Stypulkowski

Wykorzystanie badań termowizyjnych w diagnostyce elementów infrastruktury torowej
The use of thermovision tests in the diagnostics of track infrastructure elements

Jerzy Wojciechowski, Jakub Młyńczak, Marcin Gołębiowski

Jakość energii elektrycznej w odwodach zasilania urządzeń sterowania i automatyki kolejowej
Quality of electrical energy in the power supply circuits of railway signalling and automatic control devices

Jakub Młyńczak, Lucyna Sokolowska, Marcin Gołębiowski

Diagnostyka i utrzymanie urządzeń sterowania ruchem kolejowym
Diagnostics and maintenance of railway signalling and traffic control equipment

Milena Gołofit-Stawińska, Krzysztof Zboiński

Dynamika pojazdu szynowego w krzywej przejściowej powyżej prędkości krytycznej z uwagą na wężykowanie uwzględniając historię badań stateczności
Dynamics of a rail vehicle in transition curve above critical velocity with focus on hunting motion considering the review of history of the stability studies

17.00 – 18.15 Sesja II.2: Problemy decyzyjne w transporcie publicznym cz. 1

Przewodniczący: Marcin Staniek, Piotr Fołęga *Sala: Constellation 2*

Piotr Fołęga, Dorota Burchart

Zastosowanie metody LCA do wspomagania decyzji środowiskowych w transporcie publicznym
Application of the LCA method to support environmental decisions in public transport

Szymon Fierek

Harmonogramowanie pracy pojazdów transportu zbiorowego z uwzględnieniem autobusów elektrycznych na przykładzie Poznania
Vehicle scheduling for public transport buses including electric vehicles based on the example of Poznan City

Renata Źochowska, Aleksander Sobota, Grzegorz Karoń

Wpływ czasowej organizacji ruchu w sieci drogowo-ulicznej na funkcjonowanie publicznego transportu zbiorowego
The impact of temporary traffic organization in the road and street network on the functioning of public collective transport

Stanisław Ejdys

Koncepcja rozwoju transportu publicznego w Miejskim Obszarze Funkcjonalnym (MOF) Olsztyna
The concept of public transport development in the Urban Functional Area (MOF) of Olsztyn

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17.00 – 18.15 *Sesja II.3: Techniczne środki transportu*

Przewodniczący: Ewa Kardas-Cinal, Marcin Ślęzak

Sala: Constellation 3

Jerzy R. Bogdański, Mariusz Izdebski

Niepewność w określaniu stanu technicznego pojazdu

Uncertainty in determining the technical condition of the vehicle, changes in condition parameters and diagnostic parameters

Łukasz Konieczny

Modyfikacja stanowiska diagnostycznego typu Eusama umożliwiająca poszerzenie możliwości oceny skuteczności tłumienia zawieszenia pojazdu samochodowego

Modification of the Eusama-type diagnostic test stand, which allows to extend the possibilities of evaluating the effectiveness of vehicle suspension damping

Andrzej Czerepicki, Maciej Kozłowski, Andrzej Korpus

Metoda retrofitingu autobusów spalinowych

The method of retrofitting combustion engine buses

Andrzej Gągorowski

Ocena efektywności tłumika w układzie silnik – układ wylotowy

Evaluation of the muffler efficiency in the engine-exhaust system

17.00 – 18.15 *Sesja II.4: Systemy transportowe a potrzeby osób o ograniczonej mobilności*

Przewodniczący: Iwona Grabarek, Marek Karkula

Sala: Galaxy 3

Marcin Jacek Kłos, Marcin Staniek, Grzegorz Sierpiński, Ireneusz Celiński

Góry bez barier – analiza infrastruktury dla realizacji podróży fakultatywnych przez osoby o szczególnych potrzebach

Mountain without barriers - analysis of infrastructure for realizing recreational travel by people with disabilities

Beata Stasiak-Cieślak, Paweł Dziędziak, Iwona Grabarek

Funkcjonalne aspekty w innowacjach technologicznych transportu indywidualnego osób z niepełnosprawnościami

Functional aspects in technological innovations of individual transport of people with disabilities

Piotr Malawko, Anna Górska

Technika jazdy pojazdem wyposażonym w uchwyt na kole kierownicy – studium przypadku

Driving technique in a vehicle equipped with a handle on the steering wheel - a case study

Sylwia Bęczkowska, Iwona Grabarek

Dostępny transport – projektowanie uniwersalne czy inkluzywne?

Accessible transportation - universal or inclusive design?

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18.30 – 19.15 Sesja plakatowa

Przewodniczący: Adam Rosiński

Sala: Galaxy 1

Przemysław Niewiadomski, Agnieszka Stachowiak

Bariery wdrażania idei zrównoważonego wytwarzania wśród producentów części i podzespołów technicznych środków transportu rolniczego – badanie pilotażowe

Barriers to the implementation of the idea of sustainable production among producers of parts and technical subassemblies of means of agricultural transport - a pilot study

Krzysztof Blacha, Piotr Włodarski, Mariusz Wesolowski

Ocena stanu technicznego lin urządzeń awaryjnego hamowania samolotów w aspekcie bezpieczeństwa lotów

Evaluation of technical condition of aircraft arresting wire ropes in the aspect of flight safety

Elżbieta Macioszek

Czynniki przyczyniające się do śmierci pieszych w wypadkach drogowych

Factors contributing to the death of pedestrians in road accidents

Aleksandra Zabielska, Marianna Jacyna

Zastosowanie metod wielokryterialnego wspomaganie decyzji przy ocenie wyboru lokalizacji obiektów magazynowych

The use of multi-criteria decision support methods in assessing the choice of the location of warehouse facilities

Patryk Żuchowicz, Konrad Lewczuk

Zastosowanie technologii VR oraz AR w badaniu bezpieczeństwa systemów intralogistycznych

Application of VR and AR Technologies in Safety Assessment of Intralogistics Systems

Piotr Pryciński, Mariusz Duszak, Jakub Murawski, Przemysław Ilczuk

Metoda wielokryterialnej oceny możliwości dostosowania pojazdu drogowego do realizacji zadań w warunkach szynowych

Multicriteria method of assessing the adaptability of a road vehicle to perform tasks in rail conditions

Dariusz Pyza, Jakub Grudzień

Efektywność organizacji publicznego transportu zbiorowego w Polsce

The efficiency of organization of public transport in Poland

Róża Wawryszczuk, Ewa Kardas-Cinal

Wpływ czynników środowiskowych na komfort jazdy pasażera

Influence of environmental factors on passenger ride comfort

Piotr Soczówka, Renata Żochowska

Ocena lokalizacji stacji i przystanków kolejowych w aspekcie zagospodarowania przestrzennego w ich otoczeniu

Evaluation of the location of railway stops and stations in terms of land use in its their surroundings

Michał Lasota, Marianna Jacyna

Analiza organizacji i zagadnień ryzyka w trakcie przewozu ładunków ponadgabarytowych

Analysis of organization and risk issues during the transportation of oversized cargoes

Roman Sadowski, Norbert Chamier-Gliszczyński, Jerzy Fiuk

Wybrane aspekty zastosowania bezzałogowych statków powietrznych w leśnictwie

Selected aspects of the use of unmanned aircraft in forestry

Andrzej Kochan, Krystian Kwieciński, Maciej Sorokin, Tomasz Paprocki, Aneta Pogorzelska
Rewitalizacja śródmiejskich towarowych węzłów kolejowych
Revitalisation of inner-urban freight rail hubs

Hubert Rzędowski, Ewelina Sendek-Matysiak
Zagrożenia pożarowe samochodów elektrycznych typu BEV
The fire hazards associated with BEVs

Piotr Franke, Marianna Jacyna
Wybrane aspekty budowy modelu decyzyjnego dla oceny inwestycji kolejowych
Selected aspects of building a decision-making model for assessing railway investments

Jerzy Manerowski, Krzysztof Cur, Paweł Gołda, Justyna Tomaszewska, Karol Przanowski, Piotr Kaczorowski
Modelowanie predykcyjne opóźnień lotów z wykorzystaniem regresji logistycznej
Predictive modeling of flight delays using logistic regression

Daniel Kubek, Paweł Więcek
Wpływ rozkładu prawdopodobieństwa popytu w cyklu uzupełnienia zapasu na efektywność kształtowania zapasu bezpieczeństwa w warunkach niepewności
The impact of replenishment cycle demand probability distribution on the effectiveness of safety stock management under uncertainty conditions

Barbara Mazur, Mariusz Wasiak
Wybrane aspekty kompozycji floty samochodowej przedsiębiorstwa wynajmu krótkoterminowego
Selected aspects of the composition of the car fleet of short-term rental company

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9.00 – 10.30 **Sesja III.1: Problemy decyzyjne w transporcie publicznym cz. 2**

Przewodniczący: Agnieszka Merkisz-Guranowska, Piotr Kisielewski **Sala:** Constellation 1

Krzysztof Drewniok, Aleksander Sobota

Badania czasów przejazdów odcinków międzyprzystankowych – metodyka i wybrane wyniki
Research on travel times between stops - methodology and selected results

Piotr Kisielewski, Jerzy Duda, Marek Karkula, Iwona Skalna, Radosław Puka, Adam Redmer, Szymon Fierek

Optymalizacja zadań pojazdów transportu miejskiego dla dużej, mieszanej floty pojazdów i rzeczywistych ograniczeń
Optimization of urban transport vehicle tasks for large, mixed fleet of vehicles and real-world constraints

Cezary Balewski, Adam Wyszomirski, Norbert Chamier-Gliszczyński

Planowanie inicjatyw transportowych na przykładzie elektromobilności
Planning transport initiatives on the example of electromobility

Karolina Bar, Maciej Bińczak, Waldemar Walerjańczyk, Paweł Zmuda-Trzebiatowski

Modelowanie dostępności publicznego transportu zbiorowego dla osób z niepełnosprawnościami w standardzie GTFS
Modeling the accessibility of public transport for people with disabilities in the GTFS standard

Mirosław Siergiejczyk, Piotr Matysiak

Analiza porównawcza wybranych technologii dostępu radiowego w komunikacji V2X
Comparative analysis of selected radio access technologies in V2X communication

9.00 – 10.30 **Sesja III.2: Zrównoważony rozwój infrastruktury transportowej**

Przewodniczący: Piotr Sawicki, Jacek Kukulski **Sala:** Constellation 2

Hanna Sawicka, Piotr Sawicki

Projektowanie procesu obsługi pasażerów na przejściu granicznym w porcie lotniczym
Passenger Handling Process Design at the Airport Border Crossing

Konrad Lasak, Paweł Zmuda-Trzebiatowski, Hanna Sawicka, Mikołaj Schmidt

Wielokryterialna ocena infrastruktury stacji ładowania pojazdów elektrycznych w Polsce
Multicriteria Evaluation of Electric Vehicles' Charging Infrastructure in Poland

Nyelson Argolo Andrade, Hanna Sawicka

Metodyka lokalizacji parkingów Park-&-Ride
The methodology of Park-&-Ride car park locations

Edward Kozłowski, Anna Borucka, Mariola Wacewicz

Model funkcjonowania gospodarki odpadami na przykładzie miasta Lublin
Model of waste management functioning on the example of the city of Lublin

Maciej Bińczak, Marcin Kiciński, Artur Miłoszewski, Paweł Zmuda-Trzebiatowski

Alternatywne miejsca postojowe dla mieszkańców centrów aglomeracji
Alternative parking spaces for residents of agglomeration centers

Wtorek, 5 września 2023 r.

9.00 – 10.30 **Sesja III.3: *Transport drogowy a wyzwania XXI wieku***

Przewodniczący: Ireneusz Pielecha, Krzysztof Zboiński **Sala: Constellation 3**

Iouri Semenov, Marianna Jacyna, Beata Milewska

Logistyka zapewnienia dyspozycyjności floty samochodów ciężarowych oparta na zasadzie maksymalnej odporności na zdarzenia niepożądane

Truck fleet uptime logistics based on maximum resilience for adverse events

Katarzyna Markowska, Jakub Lech, Daud Khan, Beniamin Stecula

Propozycja usprawnienia wybranych systemów transportowych w przewozie towarów w transporcie drogowym – wybrane zagadnienia

A proposal to improve selected transport systems in the transport of goods in road transport – selected issues

Sławomir Tkaczyk, Mariusz Szpotański, Radosław Sędrowicz

Metoda pomiaru siły owinięcia folią stretch ładunku spaletyzowanego przy zastosowaniu autorskiego mobilnego narzędzia pomiarowego

The method of measuring the wrapping force of a palletized load with stretch foil using a proprietary mobile measuring tool

Małgorzata Grzelak, Paulina Owczarek

Analiza efektywności ekonomicznej eksploatacji floty transportowej narzędziem zapewnienia bezpieczeństwa finansowego przedsiębiorstwa

Analysis of the economic efficiency of the operation of the transport fleet as a tool to ensure the financial security of the company

Marek Karkula, Grzegorz Tarczyński, Jacek Kaleta

Optymalizacja tras dostaw paliw do stacji – analiza wrażliwości rozwiązania na zmianę poziomu akceptowalnego ryzyka

The optimization of fuel delivery routes to gas stations – a sensitivity analysis of the solution to a change in the level of acceptable risk

9.00 – 10.30 **Sesja III.4: Systemy logistyczne a wyzwania XXI wieku**

Przewodniczący: Andrzej Niewczas, Anna Borucka

Sala: Galaxy 3

Ireneusz Celiński, Grzegorz Sierpiński, Marcin Staniek, Marcin Kłos

Analiza odporności systemu transportowego w czasie działań wojennych kierowanych na wybrane obiekty infrastruktury krytycznej

Analysis of transport system resilience during hostilities directed at selected critical infrastructure facilities

Jacek Skorupski, Beata Płanda, Dominika Marzec

Ocena odporności procesu wejścia pasażerów do statku powietrznego w warunkach zakłóceń

Assessing the resilience of the passenger boarding process under disruptive conditions

Olimpia Sobczyk, Małgorzata Grzelak

Analiza wpływu konfliktu rosyjsko-ukraińskiego na bezpieczeństwo globalnych łańcuchów dostaw żywności

Analysis of the impact of the Russian-Ukrainian conflict on the security of global food supply chains

Paweł Więcek, Daniel Kubek, Jacek Kaleta

Wpływ wybranych charakterystyk szeregów czasowych na jakość prognozowania popytu na podstawie modeli autoregresyjnych i łańcuchów Markowa

The impact of time series selected characteristics on the demand forecasting effectiveness based on autoregressive models and Markov chains

Patrycja Guzanek, Anna Borucka

Efektywny proces zaopatrzenia wyzwaniem dla przedsiębiorstwa e-commerce

Efficient procurement process as a challenge for e-commerce enterprise

9.00 – 10.30 **Sesja III.5: Energy-efficient city logistics**

E-laas (polsko-chińsko-szwedzki panel dyskusyjny)

Przewodniczący: Emilian Szczepański

Sala: Galaxy 4

Wtorek, 5 września 2023 r.

10:45 – 12:00 Sesja plenarna III

Przewodniczący: **Konrad Lewczuk**

Sala: Constellation 1

Piotr Fołęga, Dorota Burchart

Ocena cyklu życia w deklaracjach środowiskowych środków transportu
Life cycle assessment in environmental declarations of transport means

Marcin Kiciński, Agnieszka Merkisz-Guranowska, Franciszek Tomaszewski, Małgorzata Orczyk

Wielokryterialna ocena systemu tramwaju towarowego – przykład miasta Poznań
Multiple Criteria Evaluation of Freight Tram System – case of the City of Poznań

Aleksander Sobota, Renata Żochowska, Grzegorz Karoń

Wybrane aspekty zmiany modelu organizacji rynku usług przewozowych w publicznym transporcie zbiorowym
Selected aspects of the change of the transport market organization model in public transport

Michał Kłodawski

Symulacyjne wspomaganie projektowania i audytu systemów logistycznych w zastosowaniach biznesowych
Simulation support for the design and audit of logistics systems in business applications

